

MODERNIZING AGRICULTURAL EDUCATION: ENHANCING PEDAGOGY and TECHNOLOGY INTEGRATION FOR TEACHING AGRICULTURAL CROP PRODUCTION NC II IN THE 21ST CENTURY

Ronald M. Cristobal

*San Mateo Vocational and Industrial High School, Schools Division of Isabela,
Department of Education, Philippines*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12073152>

ABSTRACT

This research investigates the integration of contemporary agricultural practices, including sustainable farming methods, precision agriculture, and agrotechnology. Emphasis is placed on how these innovations are incorporated into the curriculum to equip students with relevant and practical skills. This study seeks information on the perception of Grade 8 and 10 students composing of 49 participants at San Mateo Vocational & Industrial High School on the competencies of teachers in Agricultural Crop Production NC II. This study employs the Input-Process-Output (IPO) model of evaluation. The study utilized descriptive research design because the study tried to find out the competencies of teachers in teaching agricultural crop production under the Special Program of Technical Vocational Education. Descriptive research is used to describe characteristics of a population or phenomenon being studied. Since there are predefined categories, a respondent must choose from, it is considered descriptive research. These questions will not give the unique insights on the issues like exploratory research would. Instead, grouping the responses into predetermined choices will provide statistically inferable data. The data being gathered were interpreted and analyzed. Bracketing was performed to avoid bias. After data collection, the researchers found four (4) common themes. Each of these themes was discussed in terms of supporting or not supporting the review of literature. The majority of the findings of the study, supported by participants, served as authentic guidelines for the study. The fact that San Mateo Vocational and Industrial High School clearly adhere to the highest standards possible in developing its learners to be an effective part of society. It is evident from the high regard

of the respondents to the school in terms of adequacy and effectivity of its facilities and its teaching staff as well as the high regard to its administration.

Keywords: *Agriculture, Approaches and Strategies, Attitude, Crop Production, Curriculum, Department of Education or DepEd, Education, Learning, Perception, Performance, Skills, Special Program of Technical Vocational Education (SPTVE)*

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture continues to be the major and certain path to economic growth and sustainability. It encompasses all aspects of human activities. It is the act, art, a cultural necessity and science of production of goods and services through cultivation of land and management of plants and animals which creates an activity web-chain that satisfies social and economic needs.

It is opined that the last solution to our food problem would unavoidably involve the young ones (youth) who would be farmers of tomorrow. The objectives of agricultural education in secondary schools in the Philippines include stimulation of students' interest in agriculture. Enable students to acquire basic knowledge and skills in agriculture, expose students to opportunities in the field and prepare students for further studies and employment in agriculture. Because of the important role of agriculture in the development of this country, the program in Special Program for Technical Vocational Education (SPTVE), Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) and Technical Vocational Livelihood (TVL) has been undergoing development.

In the Philippine system of education, there are factors that give difficulty to the implementation of objectives. The problems of inadequately-trained teachers, lack of support either from the government or from private sector, lack of solid planning, lack of follow-up of result – all these add to the difficulty Nem Singh et al., (2019) added.

In evaluating teacher's instructional competencies Joshua et.al., (2016) emphasized the use of student achievement as the basis to assess or evaluate teachers is one of the many approaches of teacher evaluation. Other approaches in evaluating teacher's instructional competencies include classroom observation, student ratings, peer ratings, principal/HOD/administrator ratings, self-rating, teacher interview, parent rating, competency tests, and other indirect measures.

According to Arthur and Philips, competence gives the teacher the responsibility to present evidence of the achievement of the students. The question is how teachers perform, identifies the competencies and relate to overall performance of the students according to the capacity.

Also, Kyriacou said that the essence of being an effective teacher lies in knowing what to do to foster students' learning and being able to do it. Effective teaching is primarily concerned with setting up a learning activity for each student which is successful in bringing about the type of learning the teacher intends. Successful teaching is thus crucially bound up with developments on both decision-making skills and action skills. This distinction between these two types of skills is extremely important, because teaching is as much a thinking activity as it is observable actions. Developing skills as a teacher therefore is as much about developing and extending the type of decisions that teachers make about their own teaching as it is about the successful execution of those decisions.

In an interview with Brandt, Shulman pointed out that the generalizations about effective teaching from the early process-product studies had too many limitations to be a basis for information. For instance, he noted that the sampling procedures used did not give a true reflection of what a real teaching process was like. According to Shulman, there is need for "a literature that focuses on the intersection of content and pedagogy, that brings together the 'wisdom of practice' on a topic by topic, idea by idea basis" according to Brandt. Shulman viewed use of research methods such as case histories and specific stories about classroom practice as significant for enriching this 'wisdom of practice'

More so, that Agricultural Crop Production NC II is one of the subjects in Secondary Schools; and as a Vocational subject, it cannot be taught effectively without the use of appropriate instructional materials.

According to the study of Delos Santos (2013), there are factors which affect the academic performance of TLE students. Profile of the students, in terms of age, gender, occupation of parents and their educational attainment are variables that contribute to the performance of the students. Other variables are attitude of the students, parental support to the students and their performance of students in TLE.

However, Garduque (2022) in his study stated that learning theories were not enough we need to have skills to do things. Those skills are technical skills and livelihood programs which may help the students and graduates to become skilled workers of the future.

Griffith and Wade, worked on a study of The Relation of High School Career and Work-Oriented Education to Postsecondary Employment and College Performance, A Six-Year Longitudinal Study of Public High School Graduates in Maryland, USA. Employment and college enrolment history of high school graduates of a large, suburban school district were examined.

On the other hand, strong academic achievement, technical skill, certainty of occupational choice, college readiness promote degree and job attainment in careers of interest and job satisfaction helps high school graduates to enter college. It means that academic and technical skills are still essential (ACT,2019).

In a study conducted by Powell, the researcher explored how the behaviors and practices of the principals of various schools in Virginia, USA, influence and contribute to the success. The findings led to some of the following conclusions: the vision of the principal is paramount for school success, the culture of the school must be as nurturing to teachers as the students; the teaching of curriculum is foremost.

According to Parker, the Technology and Livelihood Education views the family as a major source of nurturance, protection and renewal for the individuals. As an educational force, the family significantly contributes to the qualitative development of its individual members and has the potential to prepare them for effective productivity in respect of self and society. As the relationship between the family, home & home financial matters is indivisible, so from this point of view, home financial aspects lives up to expectations through family to create adjusted relationship in the middle of individuals and social environment and hence making ready for sound human improvement.

Hence, the teaching of agriculture can be made more effective by the use of locally available aids. The persistent call by science educators as far back as two decades ago to improvise simple science equipment for use at the primary schools levels is a clear indication of their non-availability.

Thus, the advocacy to promote academic excellence and quality education in San Mateo Vocational & Industrial High School in view of making this institution a center of academic excellence in Agricultural Crop Production NC II made the researcher decide to conduct the study that will serve as a baseline for future research in agriculture education.

Research Questions

The study aims to show the respondent's perception in the following topics that relates to Agri-Crop Production education subject.

Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent level of realization of the objectives of Agricultural Crop Production NC II?
2. What is the extent state of Agricultural Crop Production education as to:
 - 2.1 Methods in Teaching
 - 2.2 Techniques in Teaching
 - 2.3 Teaching Strategies
 - 2.4 Teaching Approaches
 - 2.5 Instructional Materials used in Teaching
 - 2.6 Equipment Used in Teaching
 - 2.7 Facilities Used in Teaching
3. What are the problems encountered along the following:
 - 3.1 Student Variables
 - 3.2 Home Variables
 - 3.2 School Variables

3.3 Community Variables

4. What are the interventions implemented alongside with TLE/TVL education?

METHODOLOGY

The study utilized descriptive research design because the study tried to find out the competencies of teachers in teaching Agricultural Crop Production NC II under the Special Program for Technical Vocational Education (SPTVE) among the grade 8 and 10 students.

Descriptive research is used to describe characteristics of a population or phenomenon being studied. The main idea behind using this type of research is to better define an opinion, attitude, or behavior held by a group of people on a given subject. Consider your everyday multiple-choice questions.

Since there are predefined categories, a respondent must choose from, it is considered descriptive research. These questions will not give the unique insights on the issues like exploratory research would. Instead, grouping the responses into predetermined choices will provide statistically inferable data.

The study used a set of questionnaires that asks about the perception of the respondents on the competencies of teachers in Agricultural Crop Production NC II under the Special Program for Technical Vocational Education (SPTVE) at San Mateo Vocational and Industrial High School.

The questionnaire asks the respondents focusing on the level of competency in terms of knowledge, skills, attitude, validity of training module level of functionality and acceptability of the training module in teaching SPTVE – Agricultural Crop Production NC II.

Keeping in mind the end goal to acquire related information for this study, the specialist will use the poll as the real instrument and meetings as exploration procedures.

The researcher adopted survey questionnaires based on the purpose of the study.

The study was subjected to certain ethical issues. Prior to the conduct of the study, a request letter was given to the Schools Division Superintendent where the study was conducted. Participants were informed regarding the objectives of this study and reassured that their identity would be confidential and that the result will be used only for academic purposes. More importantly, informed consent was obtained from all the participants, this is meant for clinical studies only.

Then upon approval, the researcher administered the questionnaire to the respondents. Each respondent was be given enough time to accomplish the questionnaire.

After administering the survey questionnaire, the researcher retrieved the questionnaire. After which, the researcher tallied, computed, and analyzed the results.

Further, from the accomplished questionnaires, the data were be tallied, classified, organized, and presented in a tabular form to facilitate in-depth analysis and interpretation of data.

The following statistical tools are employed to answer the specific questions in the study. For problem 1 Frequency and percentage was used. For problem 2, 3, and 4, weighted mean, ranking was utilized.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

The presentation of the result of the study presented in table forms and were treated comprehensively.

Table 1 presents the Extent of Realization of the General Objectives of Teaching Agricultural Crop Production NC II.

Table 1
Respondent's Perception on the Extent of Realization of the General Objectives of Teaching Agricultural Crop Production NC II

Particulars	MEAN	QD	Rank
1. The teacher demonstrates an understanding of basic concepts and underlying theories in agricultural crop production.	3.77	R	6
2.The teacher demonstrates common competencies in agricultural crop production as prescribed by TESDA Training Regulations.	4.15	R	1
3.The teacher demonstrates recognizes his/her Personal Competencies and Skills (PeCS) and is able to compare these with the PeCS of a practicing entrepreneur/ employee involved in agricultural crop production.	4.13	R	2
4.The teacher demonstrates an understanding of concepts, underlying theories and principles in the use of farm tools and equipment.	3.97	R	5
5.The teacher demonstrates an understanding of estimation and basic calculation.	3.77	R	6

6.The teacher demonstrates an understanding of interpreting plans and drawings.	4.03	R	4
7.The teacher demonstrates an understanding of applying safety measures in the farm.	4.10	R	3
Average Weighted Mean	3.99	Realized	

The respondent's perception on the extent of realization of the general objectives of teaching Agricultural Crop Production NC II garnered an average weighted mean of 3.99 or "Realized." First in rank is "The teacher demonstrates common competencies in agricultural crop production as prescribed by TESDA Training Regulations" with a weighted mean of 4.15 or "Realized." Second is "The teacher demonstrates recognizes his/her Personal Competencies and Skills (PeCS) and is able to compare these with the PeCS of a practicing entrepreneur/ employee involved in Agricultural Crop Production NC II." with a weighted mean of 4.13 or "Realized." Last in rank are "The teacher demonstrates an understanding of basic concepts and underlying theories in agricultural crop production." and "The teacher demonstrates an understanding of estimation and basic calculation." with a weighted mean of 3.77 or "Realized."

This table realized that the teacher demonstrates common competencies in agricultural crop production as prescribed by TESDA Training Regulations.

Table 2
Respondent's Perception on Methods Used in Teaching Agricultural Crop Production NC II

Particulars	MEAN	QD	Rank
1. Deductive Method	3.97	E	4
2. Inductive Method	4.10	E	2
3. Project Method	4.03	E	3
4. Lecture Method	4.13	E	1
Average Weighted Mean	4.06	Effective	

The respondent's perception on the effects of methods used in teaching Agricultural Crop Production NC II garnered an average weighted mean of 4.06 or "Effective." First in rank is "Lecture Method" with a weighted mean of 4.13 or "Effective." Second is "Inductive Method." with a weighted mean of 4.10 or "Effective." Last in rank is "Deductive Method." with a weighted mean of 3.97 or "Effective."

It is evident that Lecture method is most effective used in teaching Agricultural crop production NC II.

Table 3

Respondent's Perception on the Techniques Used in Teaching Agricultural Crop Production NC II

Particulars	MEAN	QD	Rank
1. Activities suit learners' mental ability	3.97	E	5
2. Teacher with appropriate materials	3.97	E	5
3. Praises students for giving the correct response	4.18	E	2
4. Check learner's assignment	4.23	VE	1
5. Disciplines students in private	4.18	E	2
6. Conducts home visitation	4.10	E	4
Average Weighted Mean	4.11	Effective	

The respondent's perception on the effects of strategies used in teaching Agricultural Crop Production NC II garnered an average weighted mean of 4.11 or "Effective." First in rank is "Check learner's assignment" with a weighted mean of 4.15 or "Realized." Second is "Praises students for giving the correct response." with a weighted mean of 4.13 or "Realized." Last in rank are "Activities suit learners' mental ability" and "Teacher with appropriate materials." with a weighted mean of 3.97 or "Effective."

Table 4

Respondent's Perception on Strategies Used in Teaching Agricultural Crop Production NC II

Particulars	MEAN	QD	Rank
1. Uses appropriate materials	4.49	VE	1
2. Demonstrations	4.10	E	3
3. Classroom contests	3.97	E	4
4. Educational Tour	1.97	SWE	6
5. Viewing	3.77	E	5
6. Exploration	4.23	VE	2
Average Weighted Mean	3.76	Effective	

The respondent's perception on the effects of strategies used in teaching Agricultural Crop Production NC II garnered an average weighted mean of 3.76 or "Effective." First in rank is "Uses appropriate materials" with a weighted mean of 4.49 or "Very Effective." Second is "Exploration." with a weighted mean of 4.23 or "Very Effective." Last in rank is "Educational Tour." with a weighted mean of 3.76 or "Effective."

The result from the table shows that uses appropriate materials is the most effective Strategies Used in Teaching Agricultural Crop Production NC II

Table 5
Respondent's Perception on Approaches Used in Teaching Agricultural Crop Production NC II

Particulars	MEAN	QD	Rank
1. Link Approach	4.07	E	3
2. Integrative Approach	4.03	E	4
3. Learning by doing	4.08	E	2
4. Activity	4.13	E	1
5. Guided Discovery Approach	4.03	E	4
Average Weighted Mean	4.07	Effective	

The respondent's perception on the extent of approaches of the instructional materials used in teaching Agricultural Crop Production NC II garnered an average weighted mean of 4.07 or "Effective." First in rank is "Activity" with a weighted mean of 4.13 or "Effective." Second is "Learning by doing." with a weighted mean of 4.08 or "Effective." Last in rank are "Integrative Approach." and "Guided Discovery Approach." with a weighted mean of 4.03 or "Effective."

The data shows that the respondents believe that the best approach in teaching Agricultural Crop Production NC II is through activities and learning by doing which ensures that the knowledge their learned is well established into their minds.

Table 6
Respondent's Perception on the Extent of Effect of the Instructional Materials Used in Teaching Agricultural Crop Production NC II

Particulars	MEAN	QD	Rank
1. Learning Competencies (LCs)	4.23	VE	2
2. Teachers' Manual	4.10	E	3
3. Agri-Crop Reference Books	4.26	VE	1
4. Dictionary	3.74	E	5
5. Charts	3.26	E	9
6. Pocket Chart	3.49	E	8
7. Posters	3.51	E	6

8. Television	3.51	E	6
9. Overhead Projector	3.77	E	4
10. Computer	3.26	E	9
Average Weighted Mean	3.71	Effective	

The respondent's perception on the extent of effect of the instructional materials used in teaching Agri-Crop Production garnered an average weighted mean of 3.71 or "Effective." First in rank is "Agricultural Crop Production NC II Reference Books" with a weighted mean of 4.26 or "Very Effective." Second is "Learning Competencies (LCs)" with a weighted mean of 4.23 or "Very Effective." Last in rank are "Charts." and "Computer" with a weighted mean of 3.26 or "Effective."

The result shows that books are still the most important instructional material in learning Agricultural Crop Production NC II, due to activities being performed on the field which a computer is not always available to use. This coincides with the result of the computer being last on the respondent's choice.

Table 7
Respondent's Perception on the Extent of Effect of the Equipment Used in Teaching Agricultural Crop Production NC II

Particulars	MEAN	QD	Rank
1. School Farm	4.23	VE	1
2. Garden Tools	4.10	E	2
3. Field Tools	3.97	E	3
4. Apparatus	3.77	E	5
5. Models	3.85	E	4
Average Weighted Mean	3.98	Effective	

The respondent's perception on the extent of effect of the equipment used in teaching Agricultural Crop Production NC II garnered an average weighted mean of 3.98 or "Effective." First in rank is "School Farm" with a weighted mean of 4.23 or "Very Effective." This result is not surprising since the respondents are being given firsthand experience on what they will encounter doing actual work. Second is "Garden Tools." with a weighted mean of 4.10 or "Effective." Having ample time to practice skills in using garden tools is of importance for the respondents' skill to develop. Last in rank is "Apparatus." with a weighted mean of 3.77 or "Effective."

The data shows that the School farm in San Mateo Vocational and Industrial High School is the effective Equipment Used in Teaching Agricultural Crop Production NC II.

Table 8

Respondent's Perception on the Extent of Effect of the Facilities Used in Teaching Agricultural Crop Production NC II

Particulars	MEAN	QD	Rank
1. Storage Cabinet	4.22	VE	3
2. Computer Laboratory	3.85	E	4
3. Industrial Arts Room	4.23	VE	1
4. Agricultural Arts Room	4.23	VE	1
Average Weighted Mean	4.13	Effective	

The respondent's perception on the extent of effect of the facilities used in teaching Agricultural Crop Production NC II garnered an average weighted mean of 4.13 or "Effective." First in ranks are "Industrial Arts Room" and "Agricultural Arts Room" with a weighted mean of 4.23 or "Very Effective." Last in rank is "Computer Laboratory." with a weighted mean of 3.85 or "Effective."

IA room and AA rooms are the most effective way of learning Agricultural Crop Production NC II according to the respondents.

It is evident that here is where they can hone their skills into becoming professional crop producers after they graduate. Not surprising is the computer laboratory being last. Although it is still last, it still has a high rating of 3.85 but because the respondents can't really practice Agricultural Crop Production NC II in the computer lab, hence the relatively low score.

Table 9

Respondent's Perception on the Extent of Problems Encountered in Teaching Agricultural Crop Production NC II Along Student Variables

Particulars	MEAN	QD	Rank
1. Poor foundation on the four macro skills	4.28	VS	1
2. Poor study habits	2.77	MS	6
3. Absenteeism	3.36	S	3
4. Discipline	3.23	S	4
5. Comes to school unprepared	3.15	MS	5
6. Failure to submit projects on time	3.72	S	2
7. Cutting classes	2.72	MS	7
8. Vandalism	1.72	NS	9

9. Negative Attitude towards the subject	1.92	SWS	8
10. Health	1.36	NS	10
Average Weighted Mean	2.82	Moderately Serious	

The respondent's perception on the extent of problems encountered in teaching Agricultural Crop Production NC II along student variables garnered an average weighted mean of 2.82 or "Moderately Serious." First in rank is "Poor foundation on the four macro skills" with a weighted mean of 4.28 or "Very Serious." The result maybe because most of the respondents come from low-income families and can't really guide their children through their early years of education. Second is "Failure to submit projects on time." with a weighted mean of 3.72 or "Serious" The latter result is related to the first problem since projects often require certain number of resources to accomplish. Being in low-income families restricts the ability of the learners to accomplish the task. Last in rank is "Health" with a weighted mean of 3.77 or "Serious." Being raised in a low-income family also affects the health of the learner, not being able to eat nutritious food and being able to afford medicine when it is needed pose a huge problem for the learner.

Table 10
Respondent's Perception on the Extent of Problems Encountered in Teaching Agricultural Crop Production NC II Along Home Variables

Particulars	MEAN	QD	Rank
1. Dearth of reading materials	1.97	SWS	8
2. Inability of parents to pay school obligations	2.28	SWS	6
3. Parents have no time to assist their children in school activities	2.90	MS	3
4. Negative attitude of parents in attending school meetings	2.72	MS	5
5. Lukewarm attitude of parents to support programs and activities of the school	2.08	SWS	7
6. Misconception on DEPED Orders, rules and policies	1.85	SWS	10
7. Overprotective parents	1.97	SWS	8
8. Low Income Family	3.03	MS	1
9. Parents Guidance	2.90	MS	3
10. Motivation/Encouragement	2.97	MS	2
Average Weighted Mean	2.47	SWS	

The respondent's extent of problems encountered in teaching Agricultural Crop Production NC II along home variables garnered an average weighted mean of 2.47 or

“Somewhat Serious.” First in rank is “Low Income Family” with a weighted mean of 3.03 or “Moderately Serious.” Second is “Motivation/Encouragement.” with a weighted mean of 2.97 with a qualitative description of “Moderately Serious.” Last is “Misconception on DEPED Orders, rules and policies” with a weighted mean of 1.85 or “Somewhat Serious.”

The result of this table coincides with the data on the previous table in which the top problems that arise are in connection with low-income families. This may be due to the fact that San Mateo Industrial and Vocational School is a public school that caters mostly to children of farmers in which San Mateo has plenty of.

Table 11
Respondent’s Perception on the Extent of Problems Encountered in Teaching
Agricultural Crop Production NC II Along School Variables

Particulars	MEAN	QD	Rank
1. Dearth of instructional materials	2.03	SWS	2
2. Poor school potable water system	1.36	NS	10
3. Dearth of supplementary reading materials	1.72	NS	5
4. Inadequate modern facilities	1.72	NS	5
5. Inadequate reference books	1.87	SWS	4
6. Seldom does the teacher explain use behind such method	1.46	NS	8
7. Financial constraints	1.97	SWS	3
8. Activities given to students are often confined within the classroom	1.46	NS	8
9. Methods used by teachers at times are inconsistent with lesson objectives	2.23	SWS	1
10. Assignment given to students are left unchecked by teachers	1.67	NS	7
Average Weighted Mean	1.75	Not Serious	

The respondent’s perception on the extent of problems encountered in teaching Agricultural Crop Production NC II along school variables garnered an average weighted mean of 1.75 or “Not Serious.” First in rank is “Methods used by teachers at times are inconsistent with lesson objectives” with a weighted mean of 2.23 or “Somewhat Serious.” Second is “Dearth of instructional materials” with a weighted mean of 2.03 with a qualitative description of “Somewhat Serious.” Last is “Poor school potable water system.” with a weighted mean of 1.36 or “Not Serious.”

Table 12
Respondent's Perception on the Extent of Problems Encountered in Teaching Agricultural Crop Production NC II Along Community Variables

Particulars	MEAN	QD	Rank
1. Negative attitude of barangay officials to support the programs of the school	1.51	NS	8
2. Robbery	1.36	NS	10
3. Lukewarm attitude of constituents in attending school meetings and other gatherings	2.41	SWS	1
4. Unpleasant relationships between school personnel and the people	1.77	NS	5
5. Lack of modern facilities	1.79	NS	4
6. Cultural diversity	2.08	SWS	3
7. Vandalism	1.59	NS	6
8. Political interventions	1.59	NS	6
9. Religious beliefs	1.41	NS	9
10. Value of education	2.23	SWS	2
Average Weighted Mean	1.77	Not Serious	

The respondent's perception on the extent of problems encountered in teaching Agricultural Crop Production NC II along community variables garnered an average weighted mean of 1.77 or "Not Serious." First in rank is "Lukewarm attitude of constituents in attending school meetings and other gatherings." with a weighted mean of 2.41 or "Somewhat Serious." Second is "Value of education." with a weighted mean of 2.23 with a qualitative description of "Somewhat Serious." Last is "Robbery" with a weighted mean of 1.36 or "Not Serious."

Table 13
Respondent's Perception on the Interventions used in Teaching Agri-Crop

Particulars	MEAN	QD	Rank
1. Innovation on materials to be used by the teachers	4.23	SA	1
2. Localization of immersion among the students	3.90	A	5
3. Establishment of goals among the students	3.92	A	4
4. The Local Government Unit strongly supports the school	4.03	A	2
5. The administration is working closely to the teachers	4.03	A	2

6. There is an extensive training	3.23	A	7
7. Students are highly encouraged to this field	3.67	A	6
Average Weighted Mean	3.86	Agree	

The respondent's perception on the interventions used in teaching Agricultural Crop Production NC II garnered an average weighted mean of 3.86 or "Agree." First in rank is "Innovation on materials to be used by the teachers." with a weighted mean of 4.23 or "Strongly Agree." Second are "The Local Government Unit strongly supports the school" and "The administration is working closely to the teachers" with a weighted mean of 4.03 with a qualitative description of "Agree." Last is "There is an extensive training." with a weighted mean of 3.23 or "Not Serious."

The data clearly coincides with previous data on administrative support and government support of the learners of San Mateo Vocational and Industrial High School

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. The researcher conclude that the realization of the General Objectives of Teaching Agricultural Crop Production NC II is based on the common competencies that is prescribed by TESDA Training Regulations.
2. The data gathered of the study showed that San Mateo Vocational and Industrial High School clearly adhere to the highest standards possible in developing its learners to be an effective part of society. It is evident from the high regard of the respondents to the school in terms of adequacy and effectivity of its facilities and its teaching staff as well as the high regard to its administration.
3. The researcher conclude that the respondents believe that learning by doing approach using actual Agricultural Crop Production NC II tools is the most effective way of learning Agricultural Crop Production NC II.
4. The results also revealed that it was identified and examined interventions implemented alongside Technical Livelihood education (TLE) in the context of Agricultural

Crop Production NC II. The findings shed light on effective strategies and measures taken to address challenges within the educational framework.

Recommendations

From the foregoing findings and conclusions drawn, the following recommendations are offered:

1. The school administrators should continue doing their programs in lifting the quality of life of its learners. They should continue their efforts in providing adequate learning resources for their students to ensure their readiness in facing real-life situations.
2. The teachers should explore other learning methods and develop more learning materials for their students.
3. Parents/Guardians should ensure that their children have adequate financial and moral support.
4. Future researchers should expound on this study by focusing on the problems encountered and find out interventions to limit or lessen the problem.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher's unwavering commitment to ethical standards is evident in the meticulous adherence to principles of integrity, respect, and responsibility towards participants. Prior to the study, informed consent was obtained, ensuring participants' understanding of the research purpose and procedures, while maintaining confidentiality and anonymity throughout. By avoiding conflicts of interest, plagiarism, and bias, the researcher upheld the study's credibility and trustworthiness and ensured that the findings were used solely for research purposes, reflecting a dedication to ethical research conduct.

Acknowledgments

The researcher expresses heartfelt gratitude to the study participants, colleagues, friends, and beloved family for their invaluable help, support, and guidance throughout the research endeavour. Their contributions have been instrumental in the successful conduct of the study, reflecting a deep appreciation for their assistance and encouragement.

REFERENCES

- Acquisition among Technical College Graduates in Adamawa State Nigeria”
[www.erint.savap.org.pk/PDF/Vol.3\(3\)/ERInt.2014\(3.3-11\).pdf](http://www.erint.savap.org.pk/PDF/Vol.3(3)/ERInt.2014(3.3-11).pdf)
ACT (2019) “The Path to Career Success: High School Achievement, Certainty of

- Career Choice, and College Readiness Make a Difference”
www.act.org/research/policymakers/pdf/PathCareerSuccess.pdf.
- Arthur, J. and Philips, A. (2002). *Issues in history teaching*. New York : Taylor & Francis e-Library.
- Brandt, R. (2002). On research on teaching. A conversation with Lee Shulman. *Educational Leadership* 49 (7), 14-19.
- Delos Santos “Related Variables that Affect the Performance of Technology and Livelihood Education 1” Master Thesis 2013
- Garduque, Nida Soriano “Teachers’ Performance In Benigno “Ninoy” Aquino High School In Technology And Livelihood Education And Technical Vocational Education As Perceived By The Students” Dr Carlos S. Lanting College Master Thesis March 2022
- Griffith, Jane and Wade, Julie., The relationship of High School career and work oriented Education to Post secondary Employed and College Performance; A Six year Longitudinal Study of Public High School Graduates. Volume 26, Issue 3, 2011.
- Joshua, M. T., Joshua, A. M., and Kritsonis, W. A. (2016). Use of student achievement scores as basis for assessing teachers’ instructional effectiveness: Issues and research results. *National Forum of Teacher Education* Forum. Retrieved July 21, 2016, from <http://www.nationalforum.com/Electronic%20Journal%20Volumes/Joshua,%20Monday%20Use%20of%20Student%20Achievement.pdf>
- Kyriacou, C. (2011). *Essential teaching skills*. United Kingdom : Nelson Thornes Limited.
- Nem Singh, R. P., & Padilla, C. P. (2019). *Innovative teaching and evaluation*. Mandaluyong City, National Book Store.
- Parker, F.J., 2008. *Home Economics-Introduction to Dynamic Profession*. Macmillan Publishing Co. Inc., New York.
- Powell, Susan T., *Leadership and School Success: The Practices and Behavior of Principal in Successful at risk schools*. 2004.